

Physicochemical Studies on some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Palladium(0), Platinum(0), Rhodium(I) and Iridium(I) with 2-Mercapto-3-substituted-quinazolin-4-ones

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Organometallic complexes of Pt-group metals are versatile homogeneous catalyst having interesting insights into structure and bonding¹. So, starting from Malatesta compounds² $[M(P\phi)_3)_4]$ ($M = Pd$ or Pt). Vaska compound³ $[Ir(CO)(P\phi_3)_2Cl]$ and Wilkinson catalyst⁴ $[Rh(P\phi_3)_3Cl]$, we report herein some solid and stable organometallic complexes by the displacement reaction between them and 2-mercapto-3-substituted-quinazolin-4-ones (**1a** and **1b**; $R = H$ or Ph or *m*-tolyl).

Results and Discussion

Thione tautomeric form of 2-mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4-one (PQTH) and 2-mercapto-3-metatolylquinazolin-4-one (*m*QTH) replaces one molecule of $P\phi_3$ easily from benzene solution of $[Pd(P\phi_3)_4]$, $[Pt(P\phi_3)_4]$ and $[Ir(CO)(P\phi_3)_2Cl]$ but thiol tautomeric form of PQTH interacts with $[Rh(P\phi_3)_3Cl]$ resulting deprotonation of thiol hydrogen. Further replacement of $P\phi_3$ group occurs in $[Pd(P\phi_3)_4]$ and $[Pt(P\phi_3)_4]$ under more vigorous conditions by increasing the time of stirring. However, all $P\phi_3$ molecules could not be replaced

by these ligands. When substitution reaction is carried out in CS_2 , the abstraction of thiocarbonyl group occurs.

All the products obtained after carrying out substitution reactions are non-conducting in DMF and diamagnetic. The violet colour of iodine in CCl_4 was discharged by all suggesting Pd^0 , Pt^0 , Rh^I and Ir^I complexes. However, the zero-valent state of central Pd and Pt atoms was verified by iodometric and acidimetric titration⁵. Determination of univalent state of rhodium was found by titrating the complex with ceric ammonium sulphate using ferroin as indicator. The method used was described in the literature⁶. All the complexes were titrated for a two-electron charge. Thus, the known preferential tetrahedral structure for Pd^0 and Pt^0 and square-planar structure for the Rh^I and Ir^I complexes was assumed⁷.

Electronic spectra of all the complexes display very strong band of considerable high intensity at 347, 333, 340 and 253 nm in Pd^0 , Pt^0 , Rh^I and Ir^I respectively. The other ligand field bands are obscured by charge transfer band. Hence, no positive contribution is obtained in assigning structure from these spectral data.

Both PQTH and *m*QTH contain a thioamide group ($H-N-C=S$) and give rise to characteristic four thioamide bands in the infrared spectra⁸. Thioamide band-I is mixed band having contributions from $\delta_{NH} + \nu_{C=N}$, observed at 1520

TABLE I—MAJOR IR SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd*	ν _{NH}	ν _{C=O}	ν _{C≡X} (X = O or S)	Thioamide bands**				ν _{M-S} / (ν _{M-P})	ν _{M-Cl}
				I	II	III	IV		
PQTH	3 230	1 705s	—	1 520	1 290	980	800	—	—
[Pd(Pφ ₃) ₃ (PQTH)] ^a	3 245	1 710s	—	1 520	1 270	955	740	360 (420, 410)	—
[Pd(Pφ ₃) ₂ (PQTH) ₂] ^a	3 250	1 715s	—	1 525	1 270	945	745	350, 325 (430, 420)	—
[Pt(Pφ ₃) ₃ (PQTH)] ^a	3 300– 3 400	1 720s	—	1 520	1 260	950	740	345 (425, 420)	—
[Pt(Pφ ₃) ₂ (CS)(PQTH)] ^a	3 240	1 710s	1 325	1 525	1 260	950	740	345 (425, 420)	—
[Rh(Pφ ₃)(PQT)] ^b	—	1 710s	—	1 520	1 270	965	740	315 (370, 340)	—
[Ir(Pφ ₃)(CO)(PQTH)Cl] ^a	3 250	1 715s	2 180	1 525	1 265	965	745	220 (432, 420)	310 240
<i>m</i> QTH	3 220	1 710s	—	1 530	1 265	1 025	800	—	—
[Pt(Pφ ₃)(<i>m</i> QTH) ₃] ^a	3 300	1 720s	—	1 525	1 245	980	740	340, 350 (420)	—

*Nature of bonding ^athrough thione sulphur, ^bthrough thiol sulphur

**Band-I (δ_{NH} + ν_{C=N}), band-II (ν_{C=N} + δ_{NH} + δ_{CH} + ν_{C=S}), band-III (ν_{C=N} + ν_{C=S}), band-IV (ν_{C=S})

and 1530 cm⁻¹ respectively, in PQTH and *m*QTH. Agarwala and Roy⁹ on the basis of normal coordinate analysis of ethylene thiourea which contains thioamide moiety, suggested that thioamide band-I has contributions of 60–80% δ_{NH} and 12–20% ν_{CN}. The unchanged position of this band on coordination suggests the absence of bonding through imino nitrogen atom of PQTH or *m*QTH. Absence of bonding through imino nitrogen is also supported by blue-shifting of NH band of PQTH (3 230) and *m*QTH (3 220 cm⁻¹). The ν_{NH} band is observed at 3 400–3 240 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes as medium broad band. The broadness of the band is probably due to hydrogen bonding of N–H group in the crystal lattice of solid complexes.

Both PQTH and *m*QTH exhibit weak broad band at 2 340 and 2 350 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν_{SH} mode. This band is not observed on coordination indicating the presence of thione tauto-meric form of PQTH and *m*QTH in complexes and metal sulphur bond is assumed. The formation of metal-sulphur bond is also supported by the systematic change in position of all the four thioamide bands

of the ligands. The thioamide band-II (ν_{C=N} + δ_{NH} + δ_{CH} + ν_{C=S}) undergoes red-shift by 15–25 cm⁻¹, band-III (ν_{C=N} + ν_{C=S}) by 10–15 cm⁻¹ and band-IV (ν_{C=S}) by 30–40 cm⁻¹ due to increase in CN bond order and decrease in CS bond order resulting bonding through sulphur¹⁰. The ν_{CO} band of PQTH and *m*QTH observed at 1 705 and 1 710 cm⁻¹ respectively, remains almost unchanged on coordination but intensity of this band increases. This indicates absence of bonding through carbonyl oxygen of PQTH or *m*QTH.

A very strong band at 1 325 cm⁻¹ in [Pt(Pφ₃)₂(CS)(PQTH)] and medium band at 2 180 cm⁻¹ in [Ir(CO)(Pφ₃)(PQTH)Cl] suggest terminal coordinated thiocarbonyl¹¹ and carbonyl group¹² respectively. No such bands are present in the spectra of PQTH and other complexes.

Two ν_{Rh-P} (370 and 340) and one ν_{Rh-S} (315 cm⁻¹) bands in the far-infrared spectrum of [Rh(Pφ₃)₃(PQTH)] suggest two Pφ₃ groups at *cis*-position in probable square-planar configuration. Two ν_{Pd-P}

(420, 410), $\nu_{\text{Pt-P}}$ (425, 420) and one $\nu_{\text{Pd-S}}$ (360), $\nu_{\text{Pt-S}}$ (345 cm^{-1}) bands in $[\text{M}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{-(PQTH)}]$ (M = Pd or Pt) suggest C_{3v} point group in tetrahedral structure. However, two doublets at 430 and 420 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{Pd-P}}$) and two weak bands at 350 and 325 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{Pd-S}}$) suggest C_{2v} point group in tetrahedral structure of $[\text{Pd}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PQTH})]$.

In the far-infrared spectrum of $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)\text{-(PQTH)Cl}]$ the bands at 515, 500 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{Ir-C}}$), 310, 240 ($\nu_{\text{Ir-Cl}}$), 432, 420 ($\nu_{\text{Ir-P}}$) and 220 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{Ir-S}}$) have been tentatively assigned. The low position of $\nu_{\text{Ir-Cl}}$ is most probably due to high *trans*-influence of $\text{C}\equiv\text{O}$ group. It appears that Ir-C bond is stronger (515, 500 cm^{-1}) than Pt-C bond (480 cm^{-1}).

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. or C.P. grade. 2-Mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4-one (PQTH)¹³, 2-mercapto-3-metatolylquinazolin-4-one (*m*QTH)¹³, $[\text{Pd}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$ ¹⁴, $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$ ¹⁵, $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}]$ ⁴ and $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_2\text{Cl}]$ ³ were prepared by the methods described in literature.

All the complexes were prepared using a general method. A solution of $[\text{M}(\text{P}\phi_3)_4]$ (M = Pd or Pt), $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{Cl}]$ and $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)_2\text{Cl}]$ in dry benzene was mixed with ethanolic solution of the ligand in an appropriate molar ratio. The mixture was stirred for 2-3 h and then cooled in refrigerator. The complexes obtained with different metal ligand ratios, were washed with ice-cold benzene and dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 : 2-mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4-onetris(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0), $[\text{Pd}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3(\text{PQTH})]$, light yellow, m.p. 100-105° (Found : C, 71.3; H, 4.6; N, 2.2; Pd, 9.3. Calcd. for : C, 71.2; H, 4.7; N, 2.4; Pd, 9.2%); bis(2-mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4-one)bis(triphenyl phosphine)palladium(0), $[\text{Pd}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{PQTH})_2]$, mimosa colour, m.p. 180° (Found : C, 67.2; H, 4.3; N, 5.0; Pd, 9.6. Calcd. for : C, 67.4; H, 4.3; N, 4.9; Pd, 9.3%); 2-mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4-onetris(triphenyl phosphine)-platinum(0), $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3$

(PQTH)], marine grey, m.p. 187° (Found : C, 66.0; H, 4.2; N, 2.2; Pt, 16.0. Calcd. for : C, 66.0; H, 4.2; N, 2.2; Pt, 15.7%); tris(2-mercapto-3-metatolylquinazolin-4-one)triphenyl-phosphineplatinum(0), $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{-(}m\text{QTH)}_3]$, yellow, m.p. 210° (Found : C, 66.0; H, 3.9; N, 6.7; Pt, 15.3. Calcd. for : C, 59.9; H, 4.04; N, 6.66; Pt, 15.4%); 2-mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4-one thiocarbonylbis(triphenylphosphine)platinum(0), $[\text{Pt}(\text{P}\phi_3)_2(\text{CS})(\text{PQTH})]$, marine grey, m.p. 126° (Found : C, 59.0; H, 4.0; N, 3.0; Pt, 19.3. Calcd. for : C, 58.9; H, 3.9; N, 2.7; Pt, 19.1%); 2-thionato-3-phenylquinazolin-4-onetris(triphenyl phosphine) rhodium(i), $[\text{Rh}(\text{P}\phi_3)_3\text{-(PQT)}]$, buff colour (Found : C, 71.4; H, 4.8; N, 2.6; Rh, 8.7. Calcd. for : C, 71.3; H, 4.8; N, 2.4; Rh, 8.9%); chloro-carbonyl-2-mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4-onetri-phenylphosphine-iridium(i), $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{P}\phi_3)(\text{PQTH})\text{Cl}]$, vellum colour, m.p. 130° (Found : C, 51.4; H, 3.6; N, 4.0; Ir, 24.5. Calcd. for : C, 51.2; H, 3.6; N, 3.6; Ir, 24.8%).

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (dioxane) on a Carl-Zeiss (Jena) spectrophotometer. Molar conductance was measured using 10^{-3} M solution in acetone on a Wiss-Werkstätten-Weiheim obb type LBR conductivity meter.

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